

The free fall on earth's surface with rotation and numerical example

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We want to describe the motion of a falling body on earth. The gravitational force is a central force, thus:

$$\vec{F} = -m \cdot g \cdot \frac{\vec{r}}{|\vec{r}|}$$

g is the earth's acceleration and m is the mass of the falling body. The angular velocity has the form $\vec{\omega}(t) = (0, 0, \omega(t))$.

Now we introduce the centrifugal force $\vec{F}_z$ in this case:

$$F_z = m r \omega^2 \cdot \cos \alpha$$

resultant force:

$$\vec{F}_r = \vec{F} + \vec{F}_z$$

To the resultant acceleration we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} b_r(r, \alpha, \omega) &= \frac{F_r}{m} = \frac{\sqrt{F^2 + F_z^2 - 2FF_z \cos \alpha}}{m} \\ &= \sqrt{g^2 + r^2 \omega^4 \cos^2 \alpha - 2gr\omega^2 \cos^2 \alpha} \end{aligned}$$

with $r = R_p + z$. We use R_p as earth's radius and z as height. With Budo [1], §24, p.119,120 and equation (1) we get the differential equation system:

$$\ddot{\vec{r}} = \vec{b}_r(r, \alpha, \omega) + 2 \cdot \dot{\vec{r}} \times \vec{\omega} - \dot{\vec{\omega}} \times \vec{r} \quad (1)$$

with the vectors:

$$\vec{b}_r = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -b_r \end{pmatrix} \quad \vec{r} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad \dot{\vec{r}} = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{z} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\vec{w} = \begin{pmatrix} -w \cos \alpha \\ 0 \\ w \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} \quad \dot{\vec{w}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\dot{w} \cos \alpha \\ 0 \\ \dot{w} \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix}$$

The meaning of the coordinates:

x = north-south-direction (south positive)
 y = west-east-direction (east positive)
 z = height (upwards positive)

The initial conditions with the direction angle γ and throwing angle β are:

$$\vec{r}(t_0) = \vec{r}_0 \quad \vec{v}(t_0) = \vec{v}_0$$

We introduce spherical coordinates:

$$\vec{v}_0 = |\vec{v}_0| \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \cos \beta \cos \gamma \\ \cos \beta \sin \gamma \\ \sin \beta \end{pmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \gamma \in [0, 360^\circ[\\ \beta \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ] \end{array}$$

$\vec{r}(t) = (x(t), y(t), z(t))$ presents the solution of the differential equation system. Insertion of the vectors lead to the following differential equation system:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} &= 2\dot{y}w \sin \alpha + y\dot{w} \sin \alpha \\ \ddot{y} &= -2\dot{z}w \cos \alpha - 2\dot{x}w \sin \alpha - x\dot{w} \sin \alpha - z\dot{w} \cos \alpha \\ \ddot{z} &= 2\dot{y}w \cos \alpha - b_r + y\dot{w} \cos \alpha \end{aligned}$$

We have an inhomogeneous linear differential equation system of second order. $b_r = b_r(r, \alpha, w)$ and α shall be constants.

Transformation:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= a_1 \\ \dot{y} &= a_2 \\ \dot{z} &= a_3 \\ \dot{a}_1 &= 2a_2 w \sin \alpha + y \dot{w} \sin \alpha \\ \dot{a}_2 &= -2a_3 w \cos \alpha - 2a_1 w \sin \alpha - x \dot{w} \sin \alpha - z \dot{w} \cos \alpha \\ \dot{a}_3 &= 2a_2 w \cos \alpha - b_r + y \dot{w} \cos \alpha\end{aligned}$$

Then we have an inhomogeneous linear differential equation system of first order. If w is not constant, the only exact method is the expansion of series see Kamke [4], A, §2, (6.3), p.38. The alternative is a numerical calculation. If we know a fundamental system of the belonging linear homogeneous system, we can determine the solution of the inhomogeneous system with variation of constant, see Forster [2], §12, p.128, theorem 4.

If w is constant, we have a system with constant coefficients. In this case the calculation of the exact solution is possible. This is done at Grainer [3], I.2, p.8-17. This solution can be written:

$$\begin{aligned}x(t) &= b_r \cdot \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{t^2}{2} - \frac{1 - \cos 2wt}{4w^2} \right) \\ y(t) &= \frac{b_r \cos \alpha}{2w} \cdot \left(t - \frac{\sin 2wt}{2w} \right) \\ z(t) &= h - \frac{b_r t^2}{2} + b_r \cos^2 \alpha \cdot \left(\frac{t^2}{2} - \frac{1 - \cos 2wt}{4w^2} \right)\end{aligned}$$

With differentiation we get:

$$v_x = \dot{x}, v_y = \dot{y}, v_z = \dot{z}, b_x = \ddot{x}, b_y = \ddot{y}, b_z = \ddot{z}$$

s, v, b are the Euclidean norms of the pathway, the velocity and the acceleration vectors.

Now we treat the free fall from a height of 1000m with the geographic latitude = 50 degree. The rotation time of earth shall be 24 hours. It is valid $g=9.78 \frac{m}{s^2}$. The calculation leads for the first 10 seconds the following tables with pathways in metres, velocities in metres per seconds and the accelerations in $\frac{m}{s^2}$. The time is presented in seconds:

t	x	y	z	s
0	0	0	1000	1000
1	$4.258 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.529 \cdot 10^{-3}$	995.0950	995.0950004
2	$6.812 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.223 \cdot 10^{-2}$	980.3800	980.3800058
3	$3.449 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.127 \cdot 10^{-2}$	955.8550	955.8550298
4	$1.090 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.783 \cdot 10^{-2}$	921.5201	921.5200967
5	$2.661 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.911 \cdot 10^{-1}$	877.3752	877.3752441
6	$5.518 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.302 \cdot 10^{-1}$	823.4205	823.4205292
7	$1.022 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.243 \cdot 10^{-1}$	759.6559	759.6560387
8	$1.744 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.826 \cdot 10^{-1}$	686.0815	686.0819097
9	$2.793 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.114	602.6973	602.6983741
10	$4.258 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.529	509.5036	509.5058654

t	v_x	v_y	v_z	v
0	0	0	0	0
1	$1.703 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.586 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-9.809999	9.8099996
2	$1.362 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.834 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-19.619989	19.6199971
3	$4.598 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.127 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-29.429961	29.4299904
4	$1.090 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.337 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-39.239909	39.239977
5	$2.129 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.146 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-49.049821	49.049955
6	$3.679 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.651 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-58.859691	58.859923
7	$5.841 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.247 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-68.669510	68.669877
8	$8.720 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.935 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-78.479268	78.479817
9	$1.242 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.714 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-88.288958	88.289740
10	$1.703 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.586 \cdot 10^{-1}$	-98.098571	98.099643

t	b_x	b_y	b_z	b
0	0	0	-9.81	9.81
1	$5.109 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$9.171 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-9.8099957	9.81
2	$2.044 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.834 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8099825	9.81
3	$4.598 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.751 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8099614	9.81
4	$8.175 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.669 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8099314	9.81
5	$1.277 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.586 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8098928	9.81
6	$1.839 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5.503 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8098457	9.81
7	$2.503 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.420 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8097899	9.81
8	$3.270 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.337 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8097256	9.81
9	$4.138 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8.254 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8096527	9.81
10	$5.109 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$9.171 \cdot 10^{-2}$	-9.8095713	9.81

References

- [1] A Budo "Theoretische Mechanik", 10.edition, VEB Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften, Berlin, 1980
- [2] Otto Forster "Analysis 2", 5.edition, 1984, Vieweg Verlag, Brunswick
- [3] Walter Grainer "Mechanik", part 2, Verlag Harri Deutsch, 1989
- [4] Erich Kamke "Differentialgleichungen: Lösungsmethoden und Lösungen", volume 1, 10.edition, Teubner Verlag, Stuttgart, 1983
- [5] Harald Schröder "Theory of orientation" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin, 2002